

Patronage Network and Ideological Manipulations in Translation of Literary Texts: A Case Study of George Orwell's "1984" in Persian Translation in the Period 1980 to 2015

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Abstract—The process of the translation is not merely the linguistic aspects. It is also considered in the cultural framework of both the source and target text cultures. The translation process and translated texts are confronted the new aspect in 20th century which is considered mostly in the patronage framework and ideological grillwork of the target language. To have these factors scrutinized in the process of the translation both micro-element factors and macro-element factors can be taken into consideration. For the purpose of this study through a qualitative type of research based on critical discourse analysis approach, the case study of the novel "1984" written by George Orwell was chosen as the corpus of the study to have the contrastive analysis by its Persian translated texts. Results of the study revealed some distortions embedded in the target texts which were overshadowed by ideological aspect and patronage network. The outcomes of the manipulated terms were different in various categories which revealed the manipulation aspects in the texts translated.

Keywords—Critical discourse analysis, ideology, translated texts, patronage network.

I. INTRODUCTION

TRANSLATION is the process through which two different cultures are linked. The aspect of ideological constraints and the patronage network, developed in the realm of translation in the late 1970s and 1980s by the rise of descriptive approach which affected the texts.

The approach, descriptive in comparison to prescriptive, managed to meet the requirements of social aspects in the field of translation, and therefore, translation as a social activity can never be as a neutral or prejudice-free phenomenon. Translation is not just a simple communicative act, moreover, a translation never communicates in an untroubled fashion because the translator negotiates the linguistic and cultural differences [1], [2].

Cultural norms and ideologies in society introduce the translators as social agents who are constrained in many ways: by the ideology of the recipients, by the special aspects of the language constraints through which the texts are translated, by the dominant rules which are inspired by the cultural norms,

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by the patronage aspects like dominant institutions and even by the ideological frameworks of the target recipients. [3].

In the framework of the patronage, translated texts are manipulated by ideological constraints overshadowed in the translation process. The translator, as a mediator, is highly affected by the patronage network and ideological grillwork, and therefore, "from the point of view of the target literature, all translation implies a degree of manipulation of the source text for a certain purpose" [4].

A. Statement of the Problem

It is believed that the translator has the text translated through ideological aspects and forms of the target language, therefore, the terms and even the patterns of the source language are faced with manipulations which are inevitable. To have these factors considered in the process of the translation, even macro and micro elements in the translation of the source texts and translated texts can be taken into consideration. The ideology of the translator affects the translated text in the shadow of the patron and patronage network too. Regarding the point that significant studies have been devoted to the comparison of manipulatory mechanisms in translated novels during the dominance of two different ideologies, before and after the Islamic Revolution in Iran, this study sought to investigate whether the texts are manipulated differently considering both in linguistic aspect as well as the meta-text factors in Iran after the Islamic Revolution, or not.

B. Significance of the Study

The ideological aspect which is dominant in the society can affect minds, and even, it is a tool for conquering the translation field. Translated texts and translation process can never be prejudice-free. The patronage network and ideological aspects are defined as the set of norms and strategies in the society or legitimized-dominant power through which people control their manner in the life. Translation is the process of ideological-defined manner too, and therefore, translators as the mediators of the source texts and target texts, have the texts translated not only through personal ideologies but also through overshadowed ideologies in the society [5].

Manipulation in translation studies has been in the center of attention for a long time and a lot of studies are conducted to highlight the importance of this aspect in translation before

and after the Islamic Revolution in Iran. Regarding the fact that no significant studies have been conducted that focus on the process of the manipulation in both the micro and macro element aspects of the novels, this study sought to have the novels analyzed from the micro- macro aspect to determine whether the texts are manipulated differently or not.

C. Research Questions

What follows is the basic questions which the study presented seek to find the answers:

1. Which types of ideological manipulations are most commonly applied considering both the micro and macro elements in the translation of the novel "1984" in Iran through the overshadowed patronage network during the period from 1981 to 2011?
2. Which fields of subjects are most frequently manipulated in the Persian translation of the English novel "1984" in Iran?
3. Has manipulation been more common in Iran during the period from 1981 to 2011?

II. REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE

A. Overview to Translation in 20th Century

To have the term translation considered as the means through which different nations can communicate, another aspect of translation as a social activity can never be neglected. Considering the point that the practice of translating is long established, development of this field into an academic discipline was heightened in the second half of 20th century. It is considered as the time when the focus of the translation process was over the intertextual factors through which the translators were merely able to decode the source text to the target text. Therefore, the continued application of the linguistic approach and specific linguistic models such as the generative grammar and functional grammar demonstrated with translation. The cultural turn of the 1970s led to the emergence of Translation Studies as an independent discipline. The turn is also recognized as a pragmatic turn which is considered as a paradigm.

The main and most significant changes can be categorized as the shifts from: perspective, source-text oriented, linguistic approach and atomistic to the terms descriptive, target-oriented, functional and systemic [6]. The linguistic features of the text were no longer in the center of the attention; therefore, through the functional paradigm in the late 20th century, the ideological aspects along with the overshadowed patronage powers came to the fore. To have some scholars theories reviewed, the following conclusion is drawn that functional approaches are not merely based on linguistic aspects, but even on the framework of the culture, conventions, text-types, patronage and ideology.

Translation, as a process of the cultural-ideological communication, can never be objective, therefore, translators are as the mediators to decode the target-language, and target ideologies to the cultural-ideological grillwork of the source language. Therefore, certain texts which are translated could

be interpreted as instances of manipulations [7], [8]. They are social agents who are treating through different cultures and ideologies, the translated texts. The theories are selected to cover both the ideological and linguistic aspects of this study.

B. Lefevere

Lefevere describes translation as "a rewriting of an original text" (1992). In the socio-cultural aspect of the translation, it is believed that different languages reflect different values and cultures, therefore, in an attempt to mediate different languages, values or cultures, translations "nearly always contain attempts to naturalize the different culture to make it conform more to what the reader of the translation is used to" [5].

Translation is the process through which the texts communicate in the grillwork of two different cultures. Ideology and patronage are the powers which can play a great role while translating. Toury's approach was based on translated text, their process and features and functions, while on the other hand, Lefevere's viewpoint is mostly based on the ideological aspects and even the view on translation as a cultural-product of the target language. Lefevere addresses ideology and power in three different categories [5]-[9]:

- a. the translator's ideology
- b. ideological constraint by power or patronage
- c. ideological constraint initiated by the target audience.

TABLE I
 CONSTRAINTS PROPOSED BY LEFEVERE-MACRO ELEMENTS OF
 MANIPULATION

Macro-textual Elements	Prescription
Ideology	The set of beliefs and constraints of norms through which the translated texts are manipulated.
Poetics	The style and form of the literature and its function in the society.
Patronage	It is defined as the powers that influence the literary system from the outside.

C. Dukate (2007)

- 1) Text-external manipulation as conscious improvement may result from positive cultural contacts, whereby one culture consciously takes over some elements from the other [10].
- 2) Text-external manipulation as unconscious improvement is the process and the result of the process, which proceeds unconsciously and leads to improvement such as linguistic or mental enrichment.
- 3) Text-external manipulation as conscious handling are such translation related text-external processes as translation policy and conventions, which frequently manifest themselves through external guidance and meta-texts.
- 4) Text-external manipulation as unconscious handling are the unconscious approaches to translation that have been practiced for such a long time that they seem natural, for example the conventional ways of translating between the languages of smaller and bigger nations.
- 5) Text-external manipulation as conscious distortion is translation policy leading to the translation of carefully

selected authors and texts only, thus misrepresenting the source culture. The translated texts may also be accompanied by guidelines in the form of external guidance on how to perceive a particular text.

Text-external manipulation as an unconscious distortion is an automatic process and the results of such a process leads to a distorted perception of the culture(s) involved or the consequences of the lack of knowledge on the part of the text handler.

- 6) Text-internal manipulation is an all-embracing term, which denotes all kinds of manipulation, which may occur within the text. Text internal manipulation may best be explained with reference to Toury's translation laws [9]: the law of growing standardization, which describes the tendency in translation to opt for acceptability for the translation competence (TC), rather than adequacy (to the source text (ST)) especially in cultures where the status of the translation is peripheral: and the law of interference whereby the ST elements interfere with the target text (TT), thus making the text sound unnatural.
- 7) Text-internal manipulations as conscious improvement are elements that make the text clearer and more

comprehensible and acceptable to the target audience, for example through explications.

- 8) Text-internal manipulation as unconscious improvement is a type of manipulation, which can be explained with reference to Toury's [9] law of growing standardization and may be manifested through normalization.
- 9) Text-internal manipulation as conscious handling are unavoidable changes introduced due to linguistic and/or cultural peculiarities.
Text-internal manipulation as unconscious handling is a type of manipulation, due to the working of human psyche and may be manifested as errors usually due to carelessness with no serious consequences and where it is obvious that they are unintentional.
- 10) Text-internal manipulation as conscious distortion is a type of manipulation, which is due to the dominant political ideology, and may take the form omissions, additions, and substitutions and attenuations.
- 11) Text-internal manipulation as unconscious distortion is manipulation due to the translator's lack of professionalism, and is manifested as errors, which seriously mislead the reader and distort the original text.

TABLE II
DUKATE MACRO-ELEMENTS OF MANIPULATION

A General Typology of Translation - Based Manipulation (Macro-elements)	Conscious	Unconscious
As Improvement:	Enrichment due to contacts between cultures	Results and the results of process which results in improvement
As Handling:	It is defined as translation policy and conventions.	It is defined as the approaches to translation practiced for a long time, which seem merely natural.
As Distortion:	It is defined as carefully selected authors and texts.	It is defined as distorted perception of the culture due to the lack of knowledge on the part of the translator.

TABLE III
DUKATE MICRO-ELEMENTS OF MANIPULATION

A General Typology of Translation - Based Manipulation (Micro-elements)	Conscious	Unconscious
As Improvement:	The elements which make the text acceptable to target audience	It is defined as the law of growing standardization
As Handling:	Inevitable changes due to linguistic and cultural peculiarities	Unintentional and careless errors related to the human psyche
As Distortion:	Manipulation due to dominant political ideology which is shown as the form of omissions, additions, substitutions and attenuations	Manipulation due to the translator's lack of professionalism which results in misleading the reader and distorting the source language

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Method and Research Approach

This study is based on qualitative-descriptive methodology. The qualitative approach is generally correlated with the interpretive position. The interpretive approach is considered as a library research though which the data analysis and the process of collecting data are based on the theories of Translation Studies in comparison to the quantitative approach that is normative based on field work. The methodological aspect of CDA is the trajectory of the study which is based on Fairclough's approach to CDA [20], [21], critical discourse analysis. CDA is defined as an umbrella to refer to a series of theories and practices that share certain principles in terms of their approach to language study.

Fairclough's method is based on three components: description, interpretation and explanation.

B. Corpus of the Study

The novel which is focused over is "1984" written by George Orwell. To have the Persian translations observed, the comparative analysis is conducted to meet the objectives of the manipulation aspects of novels in both micro and macro element aspects after the Islamic Revolution of Iran. The English version and even the translated versions are chosen on the basis of their subject matter; that is, books were selected which discuss mostly political or ideological issues.

The details of the chosen book and its translations are followed as:

- The original version of the novel written in English: Orwell, "1984" [14].

- The translated versions of the novel written in Persian: Hoseine, "1984", Balouch, "1984"

C. Data Analysis

Due to the fact that the study is the process of micro-element and macro element probe of manipulation, so based on theories mentioned, the two translations for each selected samples were written in the form of TT1 and TT2, then the important key words of the samples were underlined to be discussed. Analysis is based on qualitative-interpretive type benefiting from the ideological theories of Lefevere and Dukate, and sampling style is purposive sampling to have the terms ideological and political covered. Finally, the conclusion section presents the in-depth discussion of the samples both at the textual and macro-element level.

Sample 1:

ST: "It was one of those pictures which are so contrived that the eyes follow you about when you move. BIG BROTHER IS WATCHING YOU, the caption beneath it ran."

TT1: ناظر کبیرمی پایدت

TT2: برادر بزرگ مراقب توست

Sample 2:

ST: "Down at street level another poster, torn at one corner, flapped fitfully in the wind, alternately covering and uncovering the single word INGSOC."

TT1: کمی پایین تر، تصویر دیگری با گوشه پاره در باد پریشان می شد و تنها واژه روی آن، سو سیانگل، به تناوب پوشیده و آشکار می گشت.

TT2: در پایین آن، نزدیک سطح خیابان، پوستر دیگری به چشم می خورد که گوشه آن پاره شده بود و باد آن را طوری تکان می داد که کلمه اینگسوس به طور متناوب آشکار و پنهان می شد.

Sample 3:

ST: "The Ministry of Truth, which concerned itself with news, entertainment, education, and the fine arts. The Ministry of Peace, which concerned itself with war. The Ministry of Love, which maintained law and order. And the Ministry of Plenty, which was responsible for economic affairs. Their names, in Newspeak: Minitrue, Minipax, Miniluv, and Miniplenty."

TT1 (Saleh Hoseini): وزارت حقیقت که با اخبار و سرگرمی و آموزش و هنرهای زیبا سرو کار داشت، وزارت صلح که به امور جنگ می رسید، وزارت عشق که قانون و نظم برقرار می کرد، و وزارت و روانی که مسئول امور اقتصادی بود. اسامی آنها در زبان جدید عبارت بودند از: وزاحقی، وزاصل، وزعشق و وزافراوانی.

TT2 (Hamidreza Balouch): (وزارت حقیقت که با اخبار و سرگرمی و آموزش و هنرهای زیبا سرو کار داشت، وزارت صلح که به امور جنگ می پرداخت، وزارت عشق که قانون و نظم برقرار می کرد، و وزارت فراوانی که مسئول امور اقتصادی بود. نام وزارتخانه ها در زبان نوین چنین بود: مینی ترو، مینی پکس، مینی لاور و مینی پلنتی).

Sample 4:

ST: "Big Brother's Order for the Day, it seemed, had been

chiefly devoted to praising the work of an organization known as FFCC, which supplied cigarettes and other comforts to the sailors in the Floating Fortresses."

TT1 (Saleh Hoseini): چنین می نمود که دستور روز ناظر کبیر عمدتاً به تقدیر از کار سازمانی اختصاص یافته بود به نام "س س د ش"، که سیگار و دیگر سوسانات ها را برای ملوانان دژهای شناور تهیه می دید.

TT2 (Hamidreza Balouch): دستور روزانه برادر بزرگ بیشتر به تقدیر از سازمانی به نام FFCC اختصاص داشت که تامین کننده سیگار و سایر وسایل آرایش ملوانان دژهای شناور بود.

Sample 5:

ST: "Except -began Winston doubtfully, and he stopped. It had been on the tip of his tongue to say 'Except the proles,' but he checked himself, not feeling fully certain that this remark was not in some way unorthodox. Syme, however, had divined what he was about to say."

TT1 (Saleh Hoseini): وینستون با تردید رد آمد که: "جز..." و سپس از گفتن باز ایستاد. کم مانده بود بگوید "جز رنجبران"، اما خودداری کرد. کاملاً مطمئن نبود که این گفته ناجور نباشد. با این حال، سایم منظور او را به فراست دریافت و با بی اعتنایی گفت:.....

TT2 (Hamidreza Balouch): سر زبانش بود که بگوید "به جز طبقه کارگر" ولی خودش را کنترل کرد. تردید داشت که شاید گفتن این حرف نشانه بی اعتقادی او به عقاید مرسوم باشد ولی سایم به فراست دریافت که او چه می خواست بگوید و با بی تفاوتی گفت:.....

Sample 6:

ST: "As usual, the face of Emmanuel Goldstein, the Enemy of the People, had flashed on to the screen. There were hisses here and there among the audience. The little sandy-haired woman gave a squeak of mingled fear and disgust."

TT1 (Saleh Hoseini): طبق معمول، چهره امانوئل گلدشتاین، دشمن قوم بر پرده ظاهر شده بود. اینجا، اینجا، پچپچه ای از حضار به گوش می رسید. زنک موحنایی از روی ترس آمیخته با نفرت جیغ زد.

TT2 (Hamidreza Balouch): طبق معمول چهره امانوئل گلدشتاین، دشمن مردم، بر پرده ظاهر شد. بعضی از حضار، دیگران را دعوت به سکوت می کردند. زن موحنایی جیغ کوتاهی ناشی از ترس و نفرت کشید.

Sample 7:

ST: "The bluebells had cascaded on to the ground. They seemed to have fallen of their own accord. He took her hand."

TT1 (Saleh Hoseini): گل ها، انگار به میل خویش، مانند آبشار از دست او فرو ریخته بودند. دست دختر را گرفت.

TT2 (Hamidreza Balouch): گل ها انگار که به دلخواه خود از دست او روی زمین ریختند. وینستون دست دختر را گرفت.

Sample 8:

ST: "... they carried on a curious, intermittent conversation which flicked on and off like the beams of a lighthouse, suddenly nipped into silence by the approach of a Party uniform or the proximity of a telescreen..."

TT1: (Saleh Hoseini): به گفت و گویی غریب و متناوب دست زدند که عین شعاع فانوس دریایی روشن و خاموش می شد، ناگهان با نزدیک شدن اونفورم حزب یا نزدیکی تله اسکرین به سکوت می گرایید.....

TT2: (Hamidreza Balouch): به نحوی عجیب و متناوب با هم صحبت می کردند. مکالمه شان با دیدن روشنایی پنجره یک خانه یا رد شدن یک نفر با یونفورم حزب و یا نزدیک شدن به صفت های سخن گو قطع می شد.....

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Macro-Element Factors

What is revealed in sample one, two and three demonstrates the role of the macro-element factors in the process of the translation. The terms: "Big brother", "INGSOC", "MINITRUE", "MINIPAX", "MINILUV" and "MINIPLenty" are considered as political and ideological words written by Orwell to convey a special message of the suffocated society of London after World War II. What follows are the factors through which the translators have the texts translated:

Big brother: The novel mainly addresses totalitarian governments and their reign in society after World War II. The term "big brother" is ironically written to convey the sense of entitlement and superiority of governors which can be considered as a meta-text factor inspired by the ideology of the author, George Orwell. The context is described in the form that a totalitarian party can create machines which perform like humans and even humans who are like machines. So the term "big brother" is chosen deliberately to convey the meaning of a suffocated society in which even thoughts and ideas can be manipulated to accept "big brother" as a superior of the whole belief system and even manners [11]. In TT2, the translator has used the transliteration method with the original word preserved in the lexical field of the source text [12], [13]. TT2 is the translated text by Hamid Reza Balouch in 2005 in Iran, while TT1 was translated by Saleh Hoseini in 1982. Therefore, TT1 has translated the text considering the facts that the recipient of the TL can feel the sense of entitlement and superiority. The translator of the TT1 has translated the text through the ideological framework of the SL more than TL.

The term "INGSOC" is the abbreviation of "English Socialism" which is expanded in one of Orwell's essays, on Notes on Nationalism. Through this essay, Orwell mentions that he had some problems related to the lack of vocabulary needed to explain an unrecognized problem which resulted in inventing the jargon of Newspeak [14]. Ingsoc (Newspeak for English Socialism or the English Socialist Party) is the political ideology of the totalitarian government of Oceania in George Orwell's dystopia novel, "1984" [15], [16]. So according to Lefevere, the ideology and patronage on the translators' part can be considered in the translation of the term; "INGSOC" which is already an ideological term according to the meta-text factors mentioned.

The actual quote from George Orwell's "1984" is: "Who controls the past controls the future. Who controls the present controls the past." The Ministry of Love MiniLuv, via

brainwashing and torture, and the Ministry of Truth MiniTrue, with propaganda, and other ministries like Ministry of Peace which is related to the war and the Ministry of Plenty which is related to the economic affairs. Therefore, the name of the ministers chosen by Orwell is a kind of ironical pattern which is related to the ideological aspect. Thus, the ideology and patronage on the translators' part can be considered in the translation of the terms mentioned.

B. Micro-Element Factors

The term "ناظر کبیر" can also be considered as a conscious improvement based on the Dukate theory. It has been chosen to make it more understandable to the target audience and to convey the original sense; however, in comparison, the translation by Balouch of "Big Brother" is just a simple word-for-word translation.

According to Dukate's conscious handling theory, both translators in question have tried to be appropriate to the source text in the translation of the term "INGSOC" due to the footnotes represented in both translations [17].

Footnote represented in TT1: (Saleh Hoseini):

در متن INGSOC. مختصر شده ی سوسیالیسم انگلیسی ، سوسیا نگل است

Footnote represented in TT2: (Hamidreza Balouch):

INGSOC مخفف English Socialism (سوسیالیسم انگلیسی)

The noticeable manipulated term in this excerpt is the acronym "FFCC". According to the source text, "...FFCC, which supplied cigarettes and other comforts to the sailors in the Floating Fortresses.", the "FFCC" might be the acronym of "Floating Fortress Cigarettes and Comforts". In an analysis of the translated texts, for TT1, the translator has made an effort to change the exotic acronym according to the target text lexical field, and thus, the Persian acronym chosen by Saleh Hoseini is a kind of word-for-word translation, as it is written in the form of "س س د ش". The acronym "س س د ش" is the abbreviated form for the terms: "سیگار، سروسات، دژهای شنو" which is the translation of the "Floating Fortress Cigarettes and Comforts". It is a kind of conscious improvement introduced by Dukate [10] due to having the exotic terms explicated which have been implicated in the source text, but in the TT2, the term "FFCC" has not even been translated by Hamidreza Balouch due to not perceiving the exact concept of the term.

According to the theory mentioned by Dukate [10], unconscious improvement, the translator, at times, translates the terms in a way which cannot be considered as a distorting process, but as a normalizing procedure. What is pointed out in the excerpt reveals that the translator of TT1 has normalized the term "prole" by writing the word "رنجبران". To have the fact considered that the term "prole" is an offensive word for working-class person or labors, so the term "رنجبران" may not convey the original message of the "prole" in the source text. It can be considered as a context-based translation, in which the term has not been distorted but normalized. As opposed to TT1, the TT2 translator has written the term "طبقه کارگر",

which might be considered more acceptable than the translation of TT1 on the part of the recipients. On the other hand, the term "unorthodox" connotes the concept of having opinions or methods which are different from what is accepted by most people. The term "unorthodox" has been translated to "ناجور" in the TT1 version, which excludes the connotative meaning of having a different opinion, and therefore, the term "ناجور" can be considered as a neutral translation.

In the excerpt, the most significant translation is that of the term: "cascade". It is a term defined as: "a small steep waterfall that is one of several together". The point elicited in this excerpt reveals that the translator of TT1 has translated the term "cascade" by proper adjective-based term in Persian written in the form of: "مانند آبشار". As opposed to TT1, the translator of TT2, Hamidreza Balouch, has simply ignored the term and there is no suitable equivalent observed in his translation; therefore, from an analysis of the text, the conclusion drawn proves that the sentence: "The bluebells had cascaded on to the ground" might have been ignored in the translation process by Hamidreza Balouch. This kind of manipulation can be categorized as an unconscious distortion, theorized by Dukate [10].

V. CONCLUSIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

An analysis of the text showed that the manipulated subjects are mostly divided to two main categories, which can be briefly discussed as:

A. Ideological Terms and Subjects

The novel "1984" is an interpretive novel which is mainly written by ideological terms, and therefore, the ideological terms and subjects have chiefly been manipulated in the translation of the novel.

B. Lexical and linguistically-Laden Subjects

From text analysis, it can also be inferred that the novel involves various figures of speech as well as different new lexical terms in the source text, which has resulted in linguistic manipulation in the translated texts in question [18].

It is believed that manipulation is an inevitable part of the translation process due to the ideological aspects as well as the patronage shadow behind the text. The manipulations applied to the texts can be divided into textual or linguistic manipulations, and even those manipulations inspired by meta-text factors [19]. From an analysis of the manipulated subjects and fields considered in this study, it can be concluded that the novel "1984", translated in the period from 1981 to 2011, has been manipulated due to the ideological and patronage factors. For certain, the literary novel "1984" involves different figures of speech which can be considered as one of the indispensable factors of the textual manipulation.

REFERENCES

- [1] Venuti, L. (2013). Translation changes everything: theory and practice. U.S.A. and Canada: Routledge.
- [2] Venuti, L. (1998). The Scandals of Translation: Towards and Ethics of Difference. London: New York: Routledge.

- [3] Alvarez, R., and M.Vidal. (1996). Translation, Power Subversion. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters.
- [4] Hermans, T. (1985). Introduction: Translation Studies and New Paradigm. In T.H. (ED), (1985). In the manipulation of literature: studies in literary translation (p.11). London: Croom Helm.
- [5] Lefevere, A. (1992). Translation, Rewriting and the Manipulation of Literary Fame. London and New York: Routledge.
- [6] Aaltonen, S. (1997) Translating Plays or Baking Apple Pies: A Functional Approach to the Study of Drama Translation. Amsterdam / Philadelphia: John Benjamins, 89-96.
- [7] Levý, J. (1967) Translation as a Decision Process. In Lawrence Venuti (ed.) (2000) The Translation Studies Reader. London and New York: Routledge, 148-59.
- [8] Pym, A. (1992) The Relations Between Translation and Material Text Transfer. Target 4:2 Amsterdam: John Benjamins B.V., 171-189.
- [9] Toury, G.(1995). Descriptive Translation Studies and Beyond. Amsterdam Philadelphia: John Benjamins.
- [10] Dukate, A. Manipulation as a Specific Phenomenon in Translation Interpreting. Retrieved August 17, 2015, from (http://www3.acadlib.lv/greydoc/Dukates_disertacija/Dukate_ang.doc Published 2007.)
- [11] Bassnett, S. (2005). Translation Studies. New York: Routledge.
- [12] Baker, M. (1992). In Other Words. Oxon: Routledge.
- [13] Baker, M. (1998). Routledge Encyclopedia of Translation Studies. New York: Routledge.
- [14] Orwell, G. (1945). "1984". London: Secker and Warburg.
- [15] Orwell, G. (Summer 1946). Why I Write. *Gangrel*.
- [16] Quinn, E. (2009). Critical Comparison to George Orwell: A literary reference to his life and work. United States of America: Facts on File, Inc.
- [17] Aixelá, J. (1995) Specific Cultural Items and their Translation. Selected Papers of the CERA Research Seminars in Translation Studies 1992-1993.
- [18] Zauberga, I. (2001) Developing Translation Competence. Rīga; N.I.M.S.
- [19] Even-Zohar, I. (1990/2000) The Position of Translated Literature within the Literary Polysystem. In: Lawrence Venuti and Mona Baker (eds.) The Translation Studies Reader. London and New York: Routledge, 192-197
- [20] Fairclough, N. (1993). Discourse and Social Change. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- [21] Foucault, M. (1972). The Discourse on Language. New York: Pantheon.